

The Influence of Work Engagement on Turnover Intention Mediated by Job Satisfaction of Bakti Timah Medika Nurses

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ABSTRACT

This research is aimed at finding out the magnitude of the influence of work engagement on turnover intention, mediated by job satisfaction. Respondents were 82 Bakti Timah Medika nurses selected through convenience sampling. The research design is quantitative with a data analysis method in the form of SEM-PLS. The research results found that work engagement had no direct effect on turnover intention. Work engagement will have a negative effect on turnover intention if it is mediated by job satisfaction. Job satisfaction fully mediates the negative influence of work engagement on turnover intention. Future research can use work stress as mediator variables. This research contributes to nursing practice regarding turnover intention through increasing job satisfaction and work engagement.

INTRODUCTION

Nurse turnover is a rapidly growing human resources problem affecting the healthcare sector worldwide. This figure is relatively high throughout the world, ranging from 15 to 44%, while in Indonesia it ranges between 13 and 35%, this figure can cause financial losses and reduce the quality of workers (Dewanto & Wardhani, 2018).

Turnover intention is the strongest cause or predictor and is closest to actual job turnover behavior (Lee et al., 2021). Nurse turnover needs to receive greater attention because it is closely related to the quality of patient care, lack of work morale and staff job satisfaction (Roche et al., 2015). The intention to leave will incur costs because nurses dedicate their time to looking for work opportunities elsewhere, become distracted at work, and can experience a decrease in productivity (Lee et al., 2021). The importance of managing staff turnover costs and the financial impact of layoffs/employee costs, which represent three times the average salary of nursing staff (Ruiz et al., 2016).

PT Pertamina Bina Medika was originally owned by PT Bakti Timah Hospital. Since the change in management there have been policy changes such as reducing nurse allowances. This allowance is part of the compensation given to nurses. Reducing the allowances or compensation provided can reduce nurses' job satisfaction and as a result the level of nurse turnover intention increases (Alam & Asim, 2019).

The level of nurse turnover intention is influenced by various factors. Job satisfaction, burnout level, psychological stress are factors in the high and low turnover intention of nurses (Labrague et al., 2020). The level of nurse turnover intention is caused by how much organizational reward is given, the level of fatigue experienced, and the level of affective commitment (Takase et al., 2015). The level of intention to change jobs depends on how much the nurse is involved in hospital affairs, the adequacy of available resources, length of work, age, professional title, education level and type of work (Chen et al., 2018).

Previous research found an inconsistent relationship between work engagement and turnover intention. Work stress and affective commitment were found to have a greater influence on turnover intention so that work engagement was found to have no effect on nurses' turnover intention (Muchtadin & Sundary, 2023). The same results were also found in previous research where work engagement had no impact on nurses' turnover intention (Edwards-Dandridge et al., 2020). These results are different in that work engagement was found to be able to reduce the level of nurse turnover intention (De Simone et al., 2018; Shahpouri et al., 2016; Wan et al., 2018). This difference in results is due to a connecting factor that makes the relationship between variables inconsistent. Other findings found that job satisfaction can explain the inconsistent influence of work engagement on nurse turnover intention (Slåtten et al., 2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Turnover Intention

Employee turnover is a serious and expensive problem due to the large costs involved in termination, advertising, recruitment, selection, and hiring. When an employee leaves an organization, the efficiency of other employees is also greatly affected (Dutta & Khatri, 2017). Turnover intention is how often individuals think and have a tendency to leave their job (Tongchaiprasit & Ariyabuddhiphongs, 2016). Turnover intention consists of the tendency to leave the organization and also the tendency to leave the nursing profession (Labrague & de Los Santos, 2021).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a nurse's positive feeling response to work conditions that meet their needs and desires, as a result of their evaluation of the value in their work experience (Liu et al., 2016). In nurses, job satisfaction is caused by factors such as stress levels, emotional exhaustion, changing work schedules, autonomy, availability of personnel resources, and cooperation (Dilig-Ruiz et al., 2018). Job dissatisfaction and fatigue are the main causes of intention to leave, absenteeism, and have a negative impact on hospital services (Koy et al., 2015).

H1: Job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention

Work Engagement

Work engagement is a condition of positive motivation in the form of vigor, dedication, and absorption (Bakker et al., 2014). Vigor or enthusiasm, is characterized by high levels of energy, mental resilience when working, willingness to put effort into work, and perseverance when facing difficulties, (2) Dedication, characterized by feelings of importance, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge, (3) absorption, characterized by full concentration and engrossment in work, feeling that time passes quickly, and difficulty disengaging from work (Schaufeli et al., 2017). Work engagement was found to have a negative effect on turnover intention (Wan et al., 2018). In contrast to previous results on nurses, work engagement has no effect on turnover intention, while job satisfaction has an effect on turnover intention (Muchtadin & Sundry, 2023). This is the basis that work engagement in nurses can influence turnover intention through job satisfaction.

H2: Work engagement has a negative effect on turnover intention

H3: Work engagement has a negative effect on turnover intention through job satisfaction

Figure 2. Research Framework

METHODOLOGY

A causal quantitative design was used in this research and data was taken over a period of time. Respondents were 82 Pertamina Bina Medika nurses. Sampling was carried out using convenience sampling. In analyzing the data, SEM PLS was used. Research data was taken via Google form. The work engagement measurement was adapted from (Schaufeli et al., 2017) which consists of three statement items. The turnover intention instrument was adapted from (Nissly et al., 2005) with four items. The job satisfaction instrument was adapted from (Chao et al., 2015) with eight items. All statements are measured with five answer choices.

RESEARCH RESULT

Respondent Description

Respondents were 25 male nurses (30.5%) and 57 female nurses (69.5%). A total of 67 people (81.7%) were born from 1981 to 1996 (generation Y), 14 nurses (17.1%) were born from 1965 to 1980 (generation X), 1 nurse (1.2%) was born in 1997 until 2012 (generation Z). A total of 51 nurses (62.2%) had a diploma education, 31 nurses (37.8%) had a bachelor's degree or D4 education. A total of 36 nurses (43.9%) had worked more than 10 years and less than 15 years, 20 nurses (24.4%) had worked more than 15 years and less than 20 years, 18 nurses (22%) had worked more than 5 years and less than 10 years, 7 nurses (8.5%) had worked more than 20 years, 1 nurse (1.2%) had worked less than 5 years.

Validity test

Table 1. Validity Test

Variabel	AVE
Turnover Intention	0.738
Job Satisfaction	0.563
Work Engagement	0.698

Based on table 1, it shows that each variable has an AVE (average variant extracted) value > 0.5 . This means that all variables in this research are considered valid.

Table 2. Outer Loadings Values

	TI		JS		WE
TI1	0.880	JS1	0.701	WE1	0.847
TI2	0.874	JS2	0.699	WE2	0.896
TI3	0.909	JS5	0.744	WE3	0.757
TI4	0.767	JS6	0.742		
		JS7	0.823		
		JS8	0.785		

In table 2, the outer loading value for each statement item from all variables is obtained. This value is obtained after removing items KK3 and KK4 which can make the AVE value < 0.5 . The outer loadings turnover intention value ranges from 0.767 to 0.909. The outer loadings value of job satisfaction ranges from 0.699 to 0.823. The outer loadings value of work engagement ranges from 0.757 to 0.896. All items were used for subsequent analyses.

Reliability Test

Table 3. Reliability Test

Variabel	Alfa Cronbach	Reliabilitas Komposit
Turnover Intention	0.880	0.918
Job Satisfaction	0.845	0.885
Work Engagament	0.785	0.873

Table 3 shows the results of reliability testing which can be seen from the Cronbach's Alpha score and composite reliability. All variables have a composite score and Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7 , which means all variables are considered reliable.

R Square Test

Table 4. R Square

Variabel	R Square
Job Satisfaction	0.099
Turnover Intention	0.237

Table 4 contains an R Square value of 0.099, which means work engagement contributes 9.9% to increasing job satisfaction. The R Square value of 0.237 means that work engagement and job satisfaction contribute 23.7% to increasing turnover intention. Other factors amounting to 72.3% are influenced by other factors.

F Square test

Table 5. f Square test

	<i>f Square</i>
WE ► TI	0.006
WE ► JS	0.110
KK ► TI	0.249

In table 5 you can see the impact of work engagement on turnover intention with an f square value of 0.006, which means it has no effect (< 0.02). The impact of work engagement on job satisfaction obtained an f square value of 0.110, which means it has a weak effect (> 0.02 and < 0.15). The impact of job satisfaction on turnover intention was found to be 0.249 (> 0.15 and < 0.35), which means it has a medium effect.

Hypothesis testing

Figure 2. Path Coefficient

Figure 1 shows the path coefficient values between variables. The influence of work engagement on job satisfaction (T = 3.113) and the influence of job satisfaction on turnover intention (T = 4.958) have a statistical T value above 1.96, which means there is a significant influence. The effect of work engagement on turnover intention has a statistical T value of 0.672 (< 1.96), which means there is no significant effect. The direction of influence can be explained at a later stage.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
WE ► TI	-0.072	0.672	0.502
WE ► JS	0.315	3.113	0.002
JS ► TI	-0.459	4.958	0.000
WE ► JS ► TI	-0.145	2.512	0.012

Table 6 shows the results of the hypothesis test where work engagement has no effect on turnover intention ($p = 0.502$; > 0.05). Work engagement has a positive effect on job satisfaction ($p = 0.002$; < 0.05). Job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention ($p = 0.000$; < 0.05). Job satisfaction fully mediates the effect of work engagement on turnover intention ($p = 0.014$; < 0.05). Full mediation occurs because work engagement cannot have a direct influence on turnover intention and work engagement will influence turnover intention through job satisfaction. The direction of influence can be seen in the original sample which has a positive or negative charge.

DISCUSSION

This research found that work engagement has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Similar findings were also expressed by previous researchers (Yandi & Havidz, 2022). The three dimensions of work engagement such as enthusiasm, dedication and absorption have a positive impact on job satisfaction (Karanika-Murray et al., 2015). Social support from colleagues, supervisor support, and work engagement are determining factors of nurse job satisfaction (Orgambídez-Ramos & de Almeida, 2017).

The results of this study reveal that job satisfaction has a negative impact on turnover intention (Table 6). These findings are in line with previous research on nurse respondents (Muchtadin & Sundry, 2023). Low job satisfaction can increase nurse turnover intention (Alsaraireh et al., 2014). A comfortable work environment can reduce turnover intentions only when the level of nurse job satisfaction is high (Al Sabei et al., 2020). One aspect of job satisfaction that needs to be considered for nurses is satisfaction with training. Satisfaction with the training received can cause workers to become more attached to their work, thereby reducing a person's intention to change jobs (Memon et al., 2016).

Previous research found that the relationship between work engagement and turnover intention is influenced by factors such as trust, work engagement (Rafiq et al., 2019). This research found that job satisfaction fully mediates the influence of work engagement on nurse turnover intention (Table 6). These results are supported by previous findings with the same results (Slåtten et al., 2022). This means that work engagement does not have a direct impact on turnover intention but has an indirect impact if accompanied by job satisfaction of Bakti Timah Medika Nurse. The influence of work engagement which is not significant on turnover intention is thought to be because the level of work stress plays a greater role in increasing turnover intention. Nurse work stress causes the nurse turnover rate to increase (De los Santos & Labrague, 2021; Fasbender et al., 2019).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this study is that work engagement has no direct effect on nurse turnover intention. Work engagement will have a negative effect on

turnover intention if it is mediated by job satisfaction. Job satisfaction fully mediates the impact that work engagement has on nurse turnover intention.

Future researchers can use variables such as work stress to mediate the influence of work engagement on inconsistent turnover intention. Management can pay attention to job satisfaction and work engagement of nurses because it can have an impact on nurse turnover intention. This research contributes to practical nursing related to job satisfaction, work engagement and nurse turnover intention.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This research was limited to nurse respondents in one hospital. Future research can use hospital workers from various professions and be carried out not only in one hospital so that the results can be more generalized.

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